

THE ACTIVE PARTICIPATION OF THE ALVEOLAR MACROPHAGES IN THE ACTIVITY OF THE THYMIC CELLS, EMPHASIZING ITS PROTAGONISM AS AN IMMUNOMODULATORY CELL

LA PARTICIPACIÓN ACTIVA DE LOS MACRÓFAGOS ALVEOLARES EN LA ACTIVIDAD DE LAS CÉLULAS TÍMICAS, DESTACANDO SU PROTAGONISMO COMO CÉLULA INMUNOMODULADORA

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ABSTRACT

The active thymus primarily functions within the course of the neonatal and pre-adolescent periods. The thymus is an organ in charge for thymocyte differentiation into immunocompetent T lymphocytes. Diverse cells in the thymus dynamically collaborate in this action, co-operating with the naive thymocytes via soluble factors, extracellular matrix (ECM) components, and microenvironment conditions. Furthermore, thymic tissue is able to be affected by a number of factors, such as the influence exerted by the rabbit alveolar macrophage on the proliferative response of thymocytes induced by the mitogen Concanavalin A (Con A). The response was measured as the incorporation of tritiated thymidine into DNA, in cultures of both cells in the presence of the mitogen. The macrophages were capable of increase or inhibit the proliferation. Thymocyte/macrophage ratios of 160:1 and 80:1 were stimulatory. The ratios of 10:1 were inhibitory and the ratios of 40:1 and 20:1 induced a double effect, stimulatory at low doses of Con A and inhibitory at high doses of the mitogen. The macrophages had to be alive to make these changes and there were no histocompatibility restrictions, since allogenic macrophages produced the same effects as autologous macrophages. The inhibitory action of thymic proliferation was reduced by irradiation (5000 R) of macrophages and by treatment with colchicine or mitomycin C. The stimulatory action was not affected by macrophage irradiation, but was increased by treatment with colchicine and mitomycin C. In conclusion, the current data firmly advise the active participation of the macrophages and/or their secretions in the physiology of the thymic cells, emphasizing its protagonism as an immunomodulatory cell.

KEY WORDS: Concanavalin A, colchicine, mitomycin C, phagocytosis, thymocytes.

RESUMEN

El timo activo funciona principalmente en el transcurso de los períodos neonatal y preadolescente. El timo es un órgano encargado de la diferenciación de los timocitos en linfocitos T inmunocompetentes. Diversas células en el timo colaboran dinámicamente en esta acción, cooperando con los timocitos “naive” a través de factores solubles, componentes de la matriz extracelular (ECM) y condiciones del microambiente. Además, el tejido tímico puede verse afectado por una serie de factores, como la influencia que ejerce el macrófago alveolar de conejo sobre la respuesta proliferativa de los timocitos inducida por el mitógeno Concanavalina A (Con A). La respuesta se midió como la incorporación de timidina tritiada al ADN, en cultivos de ambas células en presencia del mitógeno. Los macrófagos fueron capaces de aumentar o inhibir la proliferación. Las proporciones de timocitos/macrófagos de 160:1 y 80:1 fueron estimulantes. Las proporciones de 10:1 fueron inhibitorias y las proporciones de 40:1 y 20:1 indujeron un doble efecto, estimulador a dosis bajas de Con A e inhibitorio a dosis altas del mitógeno. Los macrófagos tenían que estar vivos para realizar estos cambios y no había restricciones de histocompatibilidad, ya que los macrófagos alogénicos producían los mismos efectos que los macrófagos autólogos. La acción inhibitoria de la proliferación tímica se redujo con la irradiación (5000 R) de los macrófagos y el tratamiento con colchicina o mitomicina C. La acción estimuladora no se vio afectada por la irradiación de los macrófagos, pero aumentó con el tratamiento con colchicina y mitomicina C. En conclusión, los datos actuales aconsejan firmemente la participación activa de los macrófagos y/o sus secreciones en la fisiología de las células tímicas, destacando su protagonismo como célula inmunomoduladora.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Concanavalina A, colchicina, mitomicina C, fagocitosis, timocitos.

INTRODUCTION

The thymus is a vital organ for the functions of the immune system. It governs and put on a normal

footing the total immune system and the immune organisation of the mammal's body. The capacity to increase thymus operation could be essential in an ample multiplicity of immunological diseases, and

consequently the progress of new tactics to reinforce the matured thymus must be very invaluable (Markert *et al.* 2009, Van den Brink *et al.* 2015).

Several studies involving immunological cells have established that the plant lectin Concanavalin A (Con A) links to precise locations in the plasma membrane of an ample selection of cells (Collard 1979, Gómez-Torres *et al.* 2020, Gegunde *et al.* 2021). Concanavalin A (ConA) is a lecithin-type plant protein, specifically of the L-type lecithin family, which is obtained from various species of legumes such as the *Canavalia* genus. Concanavalin A is a protein complex made up of four equal subunits, being a homotetramer, like most lecithins. Each subunit has attached metal atoms, usually manganese and calcium. Lecithins are characterized by having the ability to bind to certain carbohydrate groups in a specific way (Collard 1979), a property that is used in numerous applications, but this ability to bind carbohydrates should not be confused with glycoproteins, which are proteins that include carbohydrates in their composition.

The binding specificity of Con A is focussed to α -mannose and other oligosaccharides with alfa-D-glucosides residues that can be located in membrane glycoproteins prolonging from the plasma membrane to the extracellular areas (Collard 1979). It is known that binding of Con A to cell membranes would have physiological implication, since under experimental conditions the association of Con A with the plasma membrane induces mitotic activity in T-cells (Barnett *et al.* 1974, Pulido-Méndez *et al.* 2020) and pulmonary inflammation in rabbits after inhalation (Willoughby y Willoughby 1977).

The alveolar macrophage of the rabbit lung, influences the *in vitro* experimental proliferative response of thymocytes induced by the mitogen ConA, observing that the macrophage is able of increasing or inhibiting the proliferative capacity, depending on its concentration in the culture. The macrophage is capable of regulating the proliferation of thymocytes (Dirisala *et al.* 2013, Cho *et al.* 2021), through interaction at the membrane level at low doses (the release of soluble stimulatory factors is not excluded) (Ferone *et al.* 1999) and by secretion of soluble inhibitory factors at high doses of mitogen. On the other hand, stimulated thymocytes are able to induce phenotypic changes on macrophages (Pulido-Méndez *et al.* 2021).

In the current work, the influence exerted by the rabbit alveolar macrophage on the proliferative and/or inhibitory response of thymocytes induced by the mitogen Con A, exerting a physiological stimulus that intervenes in the normal behavior of the organ or in the pathological processes that affect it.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Animals

Male Norfolk and New Zealand rabbits weighing 2-3 kg were used.

Obtaining alveolar macrophages

The rabbits were injected intravenously with 0.3 mL of adjuvant incomplete of Freund (AIF, Difco, USA) in the marginal ear vein, to stimulate the influx of macrophages to the lung. On the fifth day after the injection, the animals were sacrificed and the lungs were removed. These were washed intratracheally with 50 mL of Minimal Essential Medium (MEM, Gibco, USA) at 37°C. The fluid extracted from the lung by this procedure was centrifuged at 1800 g for 10 min, to obtain the cell button containing the macrophages. They were washed again, centrifuged and resuspended for counting and culture. The yield was usually 0.5 mL, of packed cells (equivalent to approximately 3×10^6), with 90-95% of cells that phagocytized latex particles (Latex beads, 1.1 μ m, Sigma, USA) and viability greater than 90% by trypan blue exclusion test (Trypan Blue, Sigma, USA).

Acquiring and culturing thymic cells

Parallel to the extraction of the lungs, the thymus was extracted from the rabbits and placed in Petri dishes, containing cold MEM. It was cleaned of connective tissue, taking care to exclude the attached mediastinal ganglia, then was gently macerated with rubber policeman in cold MEM, on an ice bath. The thymocytes were washed twice with MEM by centrifugation at 1800 g for 10 min and were resuspended for viability and counting in RPMI 1640 medium (Gibco, USA), added with penicillin (100 U/mL) and streptomycin (100 mg/mL).

The thymocytes were adjusted to a concentration of 4×10^6 /mL in RPMI 1640 and 5% rabbit serum pool (previously inactivated by 56°C for 30 min). To study the influence of macrophage on the response of thymic cells, alveolar macrophages

were added to an aliquot in determined proportions and 0.25 mL of both suspensions and seeded in concave bottom culture plates, to which Con A (Grade IV, Sigma, USA) (Fig. 1) had previously been added at concentrations of 30, 15, 7.5, 3.75, 1.87, 0.94, and 0.47 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Figure 1. Structure of concanavalin A. Con A specifically binds to terminal α -D-mannosyl and α -D-glucosyl residues that may be present on carbohydrates, glycoproteins, and glycolipids. The ConA molecule has four binding sites (yellow circles), one on each subunit.

Some cultures were performed with macrophages subjected to various pre-treatments such as: *A*) Irradiation, 5000 R total dose, at 250 R/min with a source of Cobalt 60. *B*) Mytomycin C (Sigma, USA) 2 mg/mL for 1 h at 37°C, followed by 3 washes by centrifugation with MEM. *C*) Heating at 60°C, for 30 min. *D*) Colchicine (Sigma, USA) (10⁻⁵ M) with incubation for 15 min at 37°C, followed by 3 washes by centrifugation with MEM.

All cell cultures were kept at 37°C, 5% CO₂ for 48 h. At that time, they were labeled with 1 μCi / well of thymidine^{H3} (Radiochemical Amersham, USA). After an additional 18 h incubation period, cells were precipitated with water on glass fiber filters (Reeve Angel, grade 934 AH Curtin) using a cell washer (Thermo Scientific™, USA). The filters were dried for 2 hours at 60°C, placed in glass vials, to which 5 ml of scintillation cocktail (POPOP, 0.1 g, Fisher, USA) was added and the counting was carried out in a liquid scintillation counter (Packard Tricarb, USA).

The radioactivity emitted by the samples reflects the incorporation of tritiated thymidine in the thymocytes, as a result of the DNA synthesis that has occurred during cell proliferation and represents a measure of the activation or stimulation induced in culture by Con A.

The results were expressed as the average counts

x min (CPM), from the triplicates for each dose of Con A (stimulated), and were corrected by extracting the CPM obtained from the culture without Con A (controls). For the interpretation of the results, the corrected CPM, obtained from the cultures of thymocytes alone were compared with the corrected CPM, obtained from the culture of thymocytes + alveolar macrophages.

Preparation of alveolar macrophage supernatants

To study whether alveolar macrophages produce factors in the culture that act on the thymocyte response to Con A, cultures were prepared, adjusting the alveolar cells to 1 x 10⁶/mL in RPMI 1640 medium (without serum) and 3 mL of this cell suspension. They were seeded in 60 mm Petri dishes (Falcon Plastic, USA). After 1 h of incubation at 37°C, the supernatant with the non-adherent cells was discarded; 3 mL of RPMI 1640 medium was added to the adherents and they were cultured for periods of 24 and 72 h, at 37°C in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂. At the end of these periods, the supernatants were collected, centrifuged at 5000 x G and stored at 4°C, to be tested in thymocyte culture. As controls, thymocyte supernatants and RPMI 1640 medium kept at 37°C, for the same periods of time were used.

Thymocyte cultures in the presence of alveolar macrophage supernatants

The macrophage culture supernatants extracted after 24 h of culture were diluted 50% with fresh RPMI and then also added ½ to the thymocyte cultures (0.1 mL, final dilution ¼). This was carried out to roughly correspond to the amount of factor made by 25 x 10⁵ macrophages (for a ratio of T: M = 40: 1).

To explore whether the macrophage, through the interaction with Con A, released stimulating or inhibitory factors of proliferation in the medium, before culturing them, at the rate of 5 x 10⁶ macrophages in 5 mL of medium, these cells were pre-treated with Con A at a dose of 1.87 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, for 1 hr at 37°C. Then, they were washed by centrifugation and the process already described was followed.

Effects of macrophage supernatants on autologous and allogenic thymocytes

To test the effect of autologous macrophage supernatants on thymocytes, macrophages and

thymocytes without Con A were separately cultured for 24 h. After this period, the autologous and allogenic macrophage supernatant and Con A were added in the respective culture, as already described (control: thymocytes + RPMI at 37°C for 24 h).

Alterations induced by macrophages pretreated with Colchicine, Mitomycin C and Indometacin

In order to study if the modification exerted by the macrophage on the dose-response curve of thymocytes to Con A could be due to the secretion of factors to the external environment, the macrophages were treated with Colchicine, before adding them to the culture of thymocytes; 5 x 10⁶ macrophages were resuspended in 5 mL of RPMI-colchicine (2 x 10⁻³ M) and incubated for 15 min at 37°C, then they were washed with culture medium and added to the thymocytes in a proportion of 40:1.

The treatment with Mytomycin C at 50 µg/mL, which is a blocker of DNA and protein synthesis was used to 5 x 10⁶ macrophages resuspended in 5 mL of RPMI 1640, and then incubated for 45 min at 37°C with 5% CO₂, washed by centrifugation and added to the thymocyte culture in a ratio of 40:1.

The effects of the presence of indomethacin (2 x 10⁻⁶ M) (Indometacin, Sigma, USA), in the cultures of thymocytes and alveolar macrophages, were also explored, to find out if the inhibition produced by the macrophages in the proliferative response of the alveolar thymocytes, was due, at least in part, to secretion of prostaglandins into the medium.

Phagocytosis of alveolar macrophages

The phagocytic capacity of alveolar macrophages was studied by ingestion of latex particles (Rice & Fishman 1974, Filippenko *et al.* 1988, Tse *et al.* 2021).

Latex phagocytosis was performed by incubating 2 x 10⁶/mL of macrophages in RPMI 1640 medium with 20% fetal bovine serum (Gibco, USA) and 0.05 mL of 10% latex particles in saline solution. After 30 min of incubation at 37°C while shaking, the tubes were centrifuged at 1800 g to wash the cells and resuspended for counting. The number of macrophages that had ingested more than 3 particles in 200 cells were counted.

RESULTS

Effects of the addition of alveolar macrophages to thymocyte cultures

The effect of adding increasing concentrations of autologous macrophages to thymic cell culture was studied. Suspensions with thymocyte: macrophage (T: M) ratios of 160: 1, 80: 1, 20: 1 and 10: 1 were prepared and cultured by the method already described. In Table 1 can be observed that comparing the response obtained in control thymocyte culture, an increase in CPM occurred, with all the doses of Con A tested, when the addition of macrophages was in the L: M ratio. = 160: 1 and 80: 1. There was an increase in the response to Con A with low doses (0.47, 0.94 and 1.87 µg/mL) and a decrease in the response from 3.75 to 30 µg/mL, when T: M = 40.1 and 20.1 ratios were used.

Table 1. Proliferative response of thymocytes in the presence of different concentrations of alveolar macrophages (mean cpm ± S.E).

Number of Experiments	Cells	Concanavalin A doses (µg/mL)						
		0.47	0.94	1.87	3.75	7.5	15.0	30.0
3	Thymocytes	1343±22 0	5039±1019	12272±526 4	33595±648 7	54862±1004 6	73642±21505	83114±17012
3	Thym/macro f = 160:1	4286±20 4	10711±727	20902±610 3	42872±925 4	75183±1854 2	99231±28215	116638±4391 9
3	Thym/macro f = 80:1	4371±66 1	12566±281 7	28245±726 8	47893±103 3	81049±2376 4	105254±3620 2	132957±6046 5
3	Thym/macro f = 40:1	3981±84 9	10709±301 6	26634±764 4	28737±545 8	35253±4900	46509±5178	53309±5548
3	Thym/macro f = 20:1	3205±75 9	9160±2847	17964±609 3	29821±839 2	29085±9109	30555±4034	35603±5562
3	Thym/macro f = 10:1	1326±13 5	2902±150	5165±902	10502±123 0	14411±2810	17250±3306	22430±4117

Thym/macrof: thymocytes/macrophages.
Cpm: counts per minute. S.E: standard error.

A decline was observed in all doses of mitogen with a T: M = 10.1 ratio. Based on these results, the experiments were carried out using the relationship T: M = 40.1, which was where a double effect of the macrophage population began to be observed: stimulatory and inhibitory, depending on the dose of Con A.

Table 2 shows the mean of 12 experiments ± the standard error. It was observed that both, the

increase and the decrease, in the response were statistically significant ($P < 0.005$) by the *t*-student for paired samples.

In Figure 2, the dose-response curves were graphed and the stimulatory and inhibitory phases separated by an intersection point at the level of 3.75 µg/mL, where the response, seen more clearly, reached the same magnitude.

Table 2. Proliferative response of thymocytes in the presence of alveolar macrophages (Thymocyte/macrophage ratio = 40:1) (mean c.p.m ± S.E).

Exp.	Concanavalin A doses (µg/mL)													
	0.47		0.94		1.87		3.75		7.50		15.0		30.0	
	T	T+M	T	T+M	T	T+M	T	T+M	T	T+M	T	T+M	T	T+M
1	3913	8170	10587	14853	15896	24590	28095	51609	55499	48617	91374	55081	61028	45718
2	493	2851	1141	5071	2095	7339	24095	27436	25112	17613	19746	20347	43910	14377
3	1203	2781	2681	4800	5538	11443	17657	16341	19387	16807	39061	17703	28311	20395
4	-	-	-	-	1161	2404	5290	4233	13621	7563	19437	12458	21248	17180
5	-	-	-	-	5194	9074	25770	10506	33444	19494	47672	19783	31673	23545
6	-	-	3689	4220	9970	11969	24035	17293	34331	27245	40072	29729	47094	33897
7	1714	2889	3719	3911	9672	12393	31633	29353	36050	28137	47669	31610	56795	16659
8	366	725	1483	1973	6781	12621	19403	18222	47401	33462	69818	58210	103202	80122
9	766	1271	1373	4754	6401	17752	17912	25162	38545	26084	48397	44531	74049	45279
10	751	552	1753	2092	2875	4515	10093	12734	28074	9520	44431	9519	49163	11872
11	788	2289	3841	5885	5953	11385	22066	18548	35747	26854	50150	37720	64369	45752
12	993	1758	1913	5557	6407	11866	15158	17109	28664	27223	41860	27279	51176	35197
$\bar{X} \pm$	1221	2587	3218	5312	6412	11446	20101	20712	32989	24052	46641	30330	52702	32499
S.E	± 36	± 76	± 88	± 11	± 12	± 17	± 22	± 35	± 33	± 32	± 56	± 46	± 64	± 57
	$P < 0.01$		$P < 0.005$		$P < 0.005$		$P > 0.4$		$P < 0.005$		$P < 0.005$		$P < 0.005$	

Figure 2. Proliferative response of thymocytes in the presence of alveolar macrophages. (Thymocyte/macrophage ratio = 40:1). Y = counts per minute. X = Con A doses (µg/mL).

Proliferation of thymocytes in the presence of allogeneic macrophages

In order to investigate whether the macrophage-induced alteration in the thymocyte response pattern

showed histocompatibility restrictions, thymocytes were cultured in parallel in the presence of autologous and allogenic macrophages in proportions of T: M = 40: 1.

Table 3 and Figure 3 show that allogeneic macrophages produce the same type of modification as autologous macrophages. The *P* values for the tested Con A doses showed statistically significant differences, with respect to thymocytes control.

Table 3. Thymocyte proliferative response in the presence of autologous and allogenic macrophages (c.p.m ± S.E).

Number of experiments		Concanavalin A doses (µg/mL)						
		0.47	0.94	1.87	3.75	7.50	15.0	30.0
5	Thymocytes.	588±233	2894±1061	6073±746	21997±3773	44712±5210	56504±5270	64692±3858
5	Thym+ autol-mac (40:1)	2588±731	6327±1713	15468±5248	19324±3186	26539±2692	36323±2089	42102±3369
		<i>P</i> < 0.025	<i>P</i> < 0.05	<i>P</i> < 0.05	<i>P</i> < 0.025	<i>P</i> < 0.01	<i>P</i> < 0.005	<i>P</i> < 0.005
5	Thym+ allog-mac (40:1)	3367±945	6276±2052	14868±3120	16999±2109	26999±2759	32444±2459	37211±1619
		<i>P</i> < 0.025	<i>P</i> < 0.025	<i>P</i> < 0.05	<i>P</i> < 0.05	<i>P</i> < 0.005	<i>P</i> < 0.005	<i>P</i> < 0.005

c.p.m: counts per minute. S.E: standard error.
 Thym+ autol-mac: thymocytes+ autologous macrophages.
 Thym+allog-mac: thymocytes+ allogenic macrophages.

Figure 3. Thymocyte proliferative response in the presence of autologous and allogenic macrophages. Thymocyte (black square). Thym+ autol-mac: thymocytes+ autologous macrophages (light gray square). Thym+allog-mac: thymocytes+ allogenic macrophages (dark gray square).

Thymocyte cultures in the presence of alveolar macrophage supernatants

The results can be observed in Table 4 and Figure 4. The response rates of macrophages pre-treated with 1.87 µg of Con A were significantly higher than those obtained with the macrophage

supernatant pre-treated with 30 µg of Con A (*P* < 0.05). As it was observed in the 3 curves, the point where the response index is lower, coincided with the highest dose of mitogen.

Table 4. Response indices obtained in cultures of thymocytes, added with culture supernatants from alveolar macrophages.

Number of experiments		Concanavalin A doses ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			
		0.94	1.87	15.0	30.0
4	Thymocytes+macrophage supernatants not treated with Con A	0.70	0.90	0.92	0.81
		0.27	0.66	0.77	0.55
		0.56	0.63	0.45	0.24
		0.54	0.61	0.45	0.38
		(a) 0.52 ± 0.09	0.70 ± 0.07	0.65 ± 0.12	0.50 ± 0.12
4	Thymocytes+macrophage supernatants pretreated with Con A (1.87 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.01	0.82	1.03	0.72
		0.54	0.64	0.79	0.59
		1.63	1.47	0.96	0.44
		1.10	0.64	0.90	0.47
		1.07 ± 0.22	0.89 ± 0.20	0.92 ± 0.05	0.56 ± 0.06
4	Thymocytes+macrophage supernatants pretreated with Con A (30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.71	0.53	0.46	0.34
		0.96	0.84	0.55	0.38
		0.56	0.63	0.67	0.19
		0.14	0.11	0.11	0.09
		-	-	-	0.02
		-	-	-	0.26
		0.59 ± 0.17	0.53 ± 0.15	0.45 ± 0.12	0.21 ± 0.06

(a) Mean \pm S.E (standard error) of the response rates.

Response index: $\frac{\text{c.p.m corrected thymocytes+macrophage supernatants}}{\text{cpm corrected thymocytes+media}}$ for each dose of Con A

Figure 4. Response index obtained in cultures of thymocytes, added with culture different Con A concentrations supernatants from alveolar macrophage. Macrophage supernatant (dark gray line). Macrophage supernatant pretreated with 1.87 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Con A (black line). Macrophage supernatant pretreated with 30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Con A (light grey line).

Effects of viability of macrophage suspensions on the dose-response curve to Con A

It was determined, if the macrophage had to be alive or metabolically active, to produce changes in the proliferation of thymocytes. For this, thymocyte cultures were carried out in the presence of macrophages killed by prior heating to 60°C or by incubation with toxic doses (2 mg/mL) of Mitomycin C. Table 4 shows that dead macrophages are not capable of stimulating and/or inhibiting cell proliferation.

Cultures with irradiated macrophages

The alveolar macrophages at 1×10^6 /mL of RPMI 1640, were subjected to irradiation with 5000

R (source of cobalt 60), preceding to their inclusion in culture, to block processes that may depend on the synthesis of DNA and/or proteins. The viability of the trypan blue exclusion test was not affected by this procedure and was always greater than 90%.

The increase or stimulation of the proliferative response obtained with the ratio T: M = 160: 1, was not altered in the presence of the irradiated macrophages (Fig. 5). Likewise, it was observed that this stimulatory phase, at low doses of Con A, was maintained when the ratio used was T: M = 40: 1. However, the inhibitory action at optimal doses of Con A was substantially reduced by this treatment.

Figure 5. Curve Dose/response in irradiated macrophages (ratio T: M = 160: 1).

Alterations induced by macrophages pretreated with Colchicine and Mitomycin C

The viability of the macrophage suspension was checked after treatment with Colchicine and Mytomycin C and was always higher than 90%. Table 5 showed that the treatment with colchicine produced a significant over-stimulation (< 0.01; *t* Student), with the low doses of Con A, at the same

time eliminated the inhibitory effect, which appears at higher doses.

Table 5 results also indicated that the pre-treatment with Mytomycin C slightly increased the response at low doses and also suppressed the inhibitory phase, except at the dose of 6 µg/mL of Con A or by incubation with toxic doses of Mitomycin C (2 mg/mL).

Table 5. Proliferative response of thymocytes in the presence of macrophages pretreated with Colchicine (2×10^{-3} M) and Mitomycin C (50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) (mean c.p.m \pm S.E).

		Concanavalin A doses ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)						
		0.47	0.94	1.87	3.75	7.5	15.0	30.0
8	Thymocytes	523 \pm 163	2295 \pm 595	6782 \pm 132 8	14674 \pm 19 40	30429 \pm 29 15	49296 \pm 43 94	68717 \pm 28 81
8	Thymocytes+macrophages (40:1)	1476 \pm 369	4785 \pm 858	10983 \pm 18 95	14215 \pm 23 40	23956 \pm 18 64	33573 \pm 47 71	44424 \pm 39 55
8	Thymocytes+macrophages pretreated with Colchicine (40:1)	4909 \pm 118 0	9923 \pm 236 8	17683 \pm 37 42	20925 \pm 26 02	32484 \pm 45 75	47627 \pm 38 62	64384 \pm 38 52
		$P < 0.01$	$P < 0.01$	$P < 0.01$	$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.005$
8	Thymocytes+macrophages pretreated with Mitomycin C (40:1)	2368 \pm 468	6507 \pm 129 0	14966 \pm 23 59	27436 \pm 30 09	48091 \pm 59 72	58938 \pm 45 36	58449 \pm 51 64
		$P < 0.01$	$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.005$	$P < 0.005$	$P < 0.005$	$P < 0.005$

Kinetics of the proliferative response of thymocytes in cultures with alveolar macrophages

In order to explore whether these stimulatory and/or inhibitory effects induced by macrophages spread or became more pronounced over time, dose-response curves were performed in culture periods of 24, 48, 72, 96 and 120 h. Labeling with H^3 -thymidine was carried out 18 h before the culmination of these time periods.

As can be seen in Table 6 at 24 h, the response in cultures containing macrophages is similar or less than that obtained with thymocytes alone. At 48 h the double stimulatory-inhibitory effect began to be observed, dose dependent, although the differences were not significant. At 72 h the phenomenon described was already clearly apparent, but at 96 and 120 h the inhibitory phase of the response disappeared, and a stimulation with all doses of Con A (even with suppressive concentrations) was observed. The differences at 96 and 120 h were statistically significant.

Table 6. Kinetics of the proliferative response (24 to 120 h) of thymocytes in the presence of alveolar macrophages (mean c.p.m \pm S.E).

Number of experiments		Concanavalin A doses ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)							
		0.47	0.94	1.87	3.75	7.5	15.0	30.0	
5	24	Thymocytes	1063 \pm 559	2943 \pm 1006	4268 \pm 1558	6473 \pm 2833	7337 \pm 3098	7290 \pm 3049	5665 \pm 2369
		Thymocytes+macrophages (40:1)	1987 \pm 1066	3187 \pm 1279	3229 \pm 1294	4794 \pm 1989	4780 \pm 2086	3743 \pm 1189	2810 \pm 1522
5	48	Thymocytes	2092 \pm 662	5758 \pm 1698	16811 \pm 8196	26123 \pm 9737	32289 \pm 10740	37886 \pm 12648	41456 \pm 15681
		Thymocytes+macrophages (40:1)	2711 \pm 1072	8224 \pm 3108	18424 \pm 9179	23518 \pm 9334	26047 \pm 8828	30725 \pm 10652	32035 \pm 12694
5	72	Thymocytes	1327 \pm 200	2896 \pm 886	5225 \pm 1789	11464 \pm 3079	24536 \pm 6406	31529 \pm 9453	37053 \pm 13556
		Thymocytes+macrophages (40:1)	2279 \pm 629	4396 \pm 1369	9127 \pm 2875	12169 \pm 3248	16188 \pm 6182	19668 \pm 7045	19488 \pm 7270
5	96	Thymocytes	967 \pm 219	3683 \pm 898	6257 \pm 1265	12178 \pm 2036	18221 \pm 3972	24498 \pm 4907	29136 \pm 9062
		Thymocytes+macrophages (40:1)	2641 \pm 614	9647 \pm 3046	19341 \pm 4474	31791 \pm 8237	45377 \pm 3809	51091 \pm 2158	47142 \pm 9214
			$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$
5	120	Thymocytes	528 \pm 170	1149 \pm 197	1922 \pm 187	4396 \pm 895	7301 \pm 769	10989 \pm 7852	11428 \pm 2633
		Thymocytes+macrophages (40:1)	1943 \pm 391	3913 \pm 664	8652 \pm 2792	14807 \pm 2033	25970 \pm 8070	27919 \pm 7862	25341 \pm 6259
			$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.025$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$

Effects of macrophage supernatants on autologous and allogenic thymocytes

In the results (data not shown) was observed that both supernatants caused the same type of response.

Effects of macrophage irradiation on the

inhibitory action of supernatants

In the results was observed that the thymocytes interrelated with supernatants, of irradiated macrophages, reached a higher degree of response than in supernatants of non-irradiated macrophages (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Response rates obtained in thymocyte cultures with normal and irradiated (5000 R) macrophage supernatants. Normal macrophage supernatants (—). Irradiated macrophage supernatants (-----). n = 4.

Table 7. Response indices obtained in cultures of thymocytes added of cultures of alveolar macrophages pretreated with Colchicine and Mitomycin C.

Concanavalin A doses (µg/mL)	Thymocytes+ supernatant of untreated macrophages	Thymocytes + supernatant of macrophages treated with Colchicine (2 x 10 ⁻³)	Thymocytes + supernatant of macrophages treated with Mitomycin C (50 µg/mL)
1.87	0.64	2.72	1.58
	1.18	2.89	1.05
	0.70	2.47	1.90
	0.73	1.85	0.84
	1.09	1.96	1.92
	(a)0.87±0.11	2.38±0.20	1.46±0.22
	<i>P</i> < 0.005	<i>P</i> < 0.05	
30.0	0.25	0.20	0.57
	0.43	0.20	0.78
	0.42	0.42	0.96
	0.46	0.38	0.63
	0.43	0.29	0.68
	0.40±0.04	0.30±0.05	
	<i>P</i> < 0.05	<i>P</i> < 0.005	

(a) Means ±S.E of the response.

Effects of pre-treatment of macrophages with Cochicine and Mitomycin C on the production of inhibitory supernatants

In Table 7 and Figure 7 was observed that macrophage supernatants pre-treated with Colchicine and Mitomycin C, at the dose of 1.87 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Con A, caused a statistically significant increase in the proliferative response. The same supernatants at 30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ dose inhibited the proliferative response. At this dose, the degree of inhibition was approximately similar between untreated macrophage supernatants and those treated with Cochicine. In contrast, macrophage supernatants treated with Mitomycin C increased,highly significantly, response rates.

The presence of Indometacin (2×10^{-6}), was able to eliminate the inhibitory effect of high doses of Con A, and even produced an increase in the proliferative response to a dose of 15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Con A.

Figure 7. Response indices obtained in cultures of thymocytes added with supernatants of alveolar macrophages pretreated with Colchicine (2×10^{-3} M) and Mitomycin C (50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Supernatant normal macrophages (black). Supernatant of macrophages treated with colchicine (dark gray). Supernatant of macrophages treated with mitomycin C (light gray). n = 4.

Phagocytosis of alveolar macrophages

The results of 4 experiments showed a mean percentage of $90 \pm 19\%$. The macrophages that ingested more than 3 latex particles distributed throughout the cytoplasm and membranes, exceed the 90% (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Latex phagocytosis by alveolar macrophages. Pulmonary macrophages incubated with 0.05 mL of 10% latex particles in saline solution. Cells were incubated for 30 min at 37°C. After exposure to latex particles, monolayers were washed extensively to remove particles that had not been phagocytosed. The number of macrophages that had ingested more than 3 particles in 200 cells were counted. Magnification: 150X.

DISCUSSION

In the study of the effects of the addition of alveolar macrophages to thymocyte cultures, the suppressive or stimulating action dependent on the concentration of macrophages, has been described in rodent (Keller 1974, Baird & Kaplan 1977), but, the proportions of lymphocytes: macrophages (L: M) inhibitory differed. In very preliminary studies, Waldman & Gottlieb (1973) obtained inhibition with the ratio L: M = 5: 1 of peritoneal macrophages on splenic cells stimulated by DNP-BSA. On the other hand, Keller (1974) reported a stimulating effect on the proliferation induced by Con A in splenic cells, in proportions of L: M = 100: 1 and 25: 1. However, the inhibitory action observed with high doses of Con A in the ratio L: M = 40: 1, could result from the activation of a population of macrophages “*in vitro*”.

It was known (Edelson & Cohn 1974, Gemsa *et al.* 1977) that the macrophage possesses receptors for Con A, which generate changes in vacuolization, increase in adherence to glass and in pinocytotic activity, compatible with an “activated macrophage”.

Macrophages were not activated for suppression at lower doses of Con A and, therefore, continued to exert their primarial stimulating effect, due to the release of stimulatory factors, such as lymphocyte activation factor (LAF) (mitogenic protein), or by mechanisms of concentration of mitogen, at the level of its membrane, making the availability of Con A for thymocytes more effective. Macrophages are already known to possess thymocyte receptors (Lipsky & Rosenthal 1973). In the present work, we were able to observe (data not shown) the formation of rosettes of thymocytes on macrophages adhered to the culture plate. The increase in the response to Con A may also mean the acquisition of a higher stage of differentiation and maturation of thymocytes in the presence of macrophages (Pulido-Méndez *et al.* 2020). In very previous studies, Beller & Unanue (1982) described a thymic maturation “*in vitro*”, due to a product secreted by activated peritoneal macrophages, with the conversion of immature non-responding thymocytes to cells responding to phytohemagglutinin (PHA).

It is thought that the double stimulatory or inhibitory effect observed in the present work would be the balance or equilibrium point between sub-populations of macrophages, in the culture, which represents an approximation to the notion of functional heterogeneity of the macrophage. It seems logical to think, that mononuclear phagocytes constitute a cell group, as complex and heterogeneous as T or B cells populations.

According to the results with autologous macrophages was interesting to determine if there was a recognition of histocompatibility structures, in the thymocyte-macrophage interaction. The type of response obtained with allogenic macrophages was similar to that exhibited by thymocytes in the presence of autologous macrophages and suggested that these stimulatory or inhibitory effects were nonspecific and were exerted on a variety of responses.

The results, with the macrophages killed by heating or by toxic doses of Mitomycin C, indicated that the macrophage must be viable, that is, metabolically active, to produce the changes seen. In the past literature, there were contradictory reports, since Wing & Remington (1977) observed a complete elimination of the inhibitory and stimulatory effect, due to the previous heating of macrophages to 56°C for 30 min, while other authors (Ptak & Gershon 1975) found suppression of the “*in vitro*” response of antibody-forming cells against sheep red blood cells, both by living

macrophages and heat-killed macrophages, suggesting that the macrophage surface absorbs essential cooperating factors released by lymphocytes. It was already known that there are factors released by T cells, which have high affinity for macrophage cell membranes (Feldmann & Erb 1977, Freeman & Grinstein 2014).

Regarding the proliferation of the thymocytes in the presence of allogeneic macrophages was observed that these macrophages produced the same type of modification as the autologous macrophages, in terms of degree and magnitude, both of the inhibitory effect and of the stimulatory effect. The *P* values for the Con A doses tested showed statistically significant differences with respect to thymocytes alone. These results confirmed previous reports, in which allogeneic macrophages, inhibited tritiated thymidine uptake by mitogen-stimulated lymphocytes (Wing & Remington 1977, Freeman & Grinstein 2014, Sharma *et al.* 2020).

When thymocyte cultures were performed in the presence of alveolar macrophage supernatants was observed that these supernatants mimicked the inhibitory effects of macrophage cells in culture. Concerning this inhibitory effect of the supernatants was noticed that the alveolar macrophages were capable of producing inhibitory factors, without being pretreated with mitogen. However, the production of this inhibitory factor was increased, if the macrophages were treated with high doses of Con A (3 µg/mL). These data constituted evidence that the inhibitory effects caused by macrophages, at optimal doses of Con A, were due to the secretion of soluble suppressive factors, which preferentially affect cells with a high rate of proliferation.

Irradiated macrophages produced supernatants with less proliferative response inhibitory capacity than non-irradiated macrophages.

It can be argued that irradiated macrophages pretreated with Con A would eliminate Con A in culture by binding it to their surface. This could indicate the activation of macrophages by irradiation and increased production of a stimulating factor or blockage of the production of a suppressing factor by inhibition of DNA synthesis. The mature and fixed macrophages in the tissues do not synthesize DNA, so this action is exerted on the recent origin juvenile macrophages that go to the lung.

Apropos the alterations induced by macrophages

pretreated with Colchicine, the supernatant of these macrophages caused an increase in the response to the dose of 1.87 µg/mL of Con A, Colchicine affects the microtubule system and its assembly, thus compromising the cellular systems of secretion. This opens the possibility that under these conditions, the macrophages increase the release of stimulant soluble factors. If this were the case, the stimulation at low doses of Con A would not only be due to the effects of mitogen concentration on the macrophage membrane, but also to the increase in some activating product in the medium. It is interesting, the fact that in this supernatant, the inhibitory activity was also expressed at high doses of Con A.

The action of Colchicine is not easily reversible; It had already been described that colchicine can exert a stimulating effect on cell proliferation (Stenzel *et al.* 1978), in response to a variety of stimuli, although not in response to Con A.

These results advise a selective stimulatory effect of colchicine on cellular responses provoked by cell-cell contact. Mediators that transform microtubular assemblies might regulate the stimulation of immune responses that implicate cellular interactions. The capacity of colchicine to inhibit DNA synthesis in Con A-stimulated human cells would seem to be an indirect result of disassembly of microtubules (Rudd & Kaplan 1981).

Considering macrophages pretreated with Mitomycin C, they produced supernatants that showed a large decrease in their suppressive activity, even at a dose of 30 µg/mL of Con A, and an increased response to a dose of 1.87 µg/mL. These results coincided with those of the irradiated macrophages and can be explained by the blockage in DNA synthesis in the production of a cell proliferation suppressor factor.

It could be said that the supernatants of macrophage cultures, subjected to the same treatments as the cells that are added to the thymocytes, mimic their effects in what refers to the inhibitory phase of the response and it is concluded that the effect suppressor of the macrophage, in this experimental system it is due to the secretion of soluble factors (Cho *et al.* 2021), probably of a diverse nature, among could be Prostaglandin E2, which is produced by macrophages. It has been demonstrated that signaling through the E-type receptors stimulated the expression of the anti-inflammatory factors, which have shown to be

essential for macrophage differentiation (Basile 2022). The inhibitory or stimulant effects of the Indometacin suggest that the secretion of prostaglandins by the alveolar macrophage constitutes a mechanism of inhibitory action exerted at high doses of Con A, on the proliferation of thymocytes. However, it is not excluded that other inhibitory factors, other than prostaglandins, were being secreted by the macrophage (Song *et al.* 2022).

The mechanisms by which prostaglandins inhibit thymocyte proliferation are probably related to the stimulation of adenylyl cyclase and increased cyclic AMP (Epstein *et al.* 1971, Strom *et al.* 1972, Zimmermann *et al.* 2022), which prevents cell transformation.

In closure, the current paper showed the thymocytes responses by the action of macrophages stimulated with Con A, analyzed in terms of a cooperative phenomenon between thymocytes, and lung macrophages accessory cells. Thymocytes respond with proliferative or inhibitory actions to macrophages influenced by different drugs and radiation (Makarova & Postovalova 2017). Small numbers of thymocytes respond to macrophage-stimulated with Con A at 24 h. By increasing the incubation time, sensitivity to Con A appears. This response may be linked either to the increase in a minor responding population. We discuss the fact that the behaviour of the thymocytes after activation allow us to deduce the percentage of cooperation (proliferation/inhibition) produced by the co-culture. Cooperation with thymocytes or the presence of active macrophage cells possibly are able to convert the thymocyte expression during co-culture experiments.

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